

Mystery Dust-jacket

Recently, while going through my papers, I found this manuscript written on old tin leather. Probably got it at a flea-market some time ago but I don't remember exactly when and where. It came as a dust-jacket for some other book, and I removed it but didn't bother to find more about it. It seems to have been written in the Latin alphabet a long time ago. Perhaps someone might be able to tell more about it, like its date, the language it is written in (French?) and what it is about.

by Henry Currier & his heirs plus en
right of the said Robert Currier
of the County of York in the State of New York
the said Currier assigns the same to
the said John Currier & his heirs
and the said John Currier & his heirs
assigns the same to the said Robert Currier
of the County of York in the State of New York
the said Currier assigns the same to
the said John Currier & his heirs
and the said John Currier & his heirs
assigns the same to the said Robert Currier
of the County of York in the State of New York

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[Faint, illegible handwritten text on aged, stained paper]